

Partial specific volumes ($\bar{v}_o$) were pycnometrically determined⁶, using equation (5),

$$\bar{v}_o = (1/d_o) (1 - \Delta d/C) \quad (5)$$

Plot of $(1/d_o) (1 - \Delta d/C)$ vs C extrapolated to zero concentration, gave the value of $\bar{v}_o$, where d_o is density of the solvent (g ml^{-1}), d the density of solution (g ml^{-1}), $\Delta d = d - d_o$, and C the concentration of protein (g ml^{-1}). Protein content (C) of the solution was estimated gravimetrically by initially keeping the proteins at 60° overnight followed by drying at 100° to constant weight,

Intrinsic $[\eta]$, kinematic $[\eta/d]$ and relative viscosities (η_{rel}) were determined using multigradient Ubbelohde viscometer^{7,8}. Tanford⁹ equation,

$$[\eta] = [\eta/d] + \frac{1}{d_o} (1 - \bar{v}_o d_o) \quad (6)$$

was used to calculate $\bar{v}_o$. The plots of equation (3) were found to be hyperbolic. Value of V_E was obtained using Lagrange's equation¹⁰. Simha equation⁵ (4) was used for computing ν . The equation¹¹,

$$f/f_o = F \left(\frac{V_E}{\bar{v}_o} \right)^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

was used to calculate the frictional coefficient ratio f/f_o and F is a function of axial ratio¹². Axial ratios (a/b) were calculated¹³ from the value of F .

Results and Discussion

The various respective experimental parameters (40°) of albumin, hemoglobin and egg albumin are presented in Table 1. With the decrease in concentration of protein in solution, the values of partial

specific volumes increased and viscosities decreased. The slope for the determination of partial specific volumes and intrinsic and kinematic viscosities of the experimental proteins indicated the extensive solute-solute interactions in the solutions of sample proteins. The experimental and reported (Table 1) values of different parameters are in agreement. This approach is unique because of simplicity and rapidity of experimentation. It enables the determination of size and shapes of near-spherical macromolecules in solutions under different physiological conditions.

References

1. B. K. DEWAN, V. A. BLOOMFIELD, A. CHUDGAR and C. V. MORR, *J. Dairy Sci.*, 1978, **56**, 699.
2. M. EILERS, *Kolloid Z.*, 1941, **97**, 818.
3. M. EILERS, *Kolloid Z.*, 1942, **102**, 154.
4. A. S. NARANG, G. S. BAINS and I. S. BHATIA, *Cereal Chem.*, 1981, **10**, 92.
5. R. SIMHA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, **44**, 25.
6. P. A. CHARLEWOOD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 776.
7. A. TAKAHASHI and M. NAGASAWA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 549.
8. J. H. LARKIN, J. D. PERRINGS, G. R. SHEPHERD and B. J. NALAND, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1965, **42**, 555.
9. C. TANFORD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 798.
10. E. V. KRISHNAMURTHY and S. K. SEN, "Computer Based Numerical Algorithms", East-West Printers, New Delhi, 1976.
11. I. D. KUNTZ and W. KAUFMANN, *Adv. Protein Chem.*, 1974, **28**, 239.
12. H. A. SCHERAGA, "Protein Structure", Academic, New York, 1961, p. 18.
13. C. TANFORD, *Adv. Protein Chem.*, 1968, **23**, 121.
14. A. G. POLSON, *Kolloid Z.*, 1939, **88**, 51.
15. C. TANFORD and J. G. BUZZELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 225.

TABLE 1—LITERATURE AND EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Proteins (mol. wt.)		
	Bovine serum albumin (89000)	Hemoglobin (64500)	Egg albumin (45000)
$\bar{v}_o$ (ml g^{-1}) ^a	0.712	0.757	0.725
$\bar{v}_o$ (ml g^{-1}) ^{b,1}	0.708	0.758	0.718
$[\eta]$ (ml g^{-1}) ^a	4.0	3.5	3.4
$[\eta]$ (ml g^{-1}) ²	3.7 ^a	3.6 ^b	4.0 ¹
$[\eta/d]$ (ml g^{-1}) ^a	3.7	3.25	3.15
V_E (ml g^{-1}) ^a	1.26	1.05	0.79
V_E (ml g^{-1}) ^{b,2}	1.12	1.09	0.85
ν^a	3.25	3.86	4.81
$\nu^{b,2}$	3.30	3.30	4.66
(from axial ratios)			
$f/f_o^{b,2}$	1.31	1.22	1.23
(from diffusion coeff.)			
$f/f_o^{b,2}$	1.33	1.28	1.19
(from sedimentation coeff.)			
$f/f_o^{b,1}$	1.36	1.26	1.24
a/b^a	2.4	2.6	3.9
$a/b^{b,2}$	2.5	2.5	4.0

^a Experimental value. ^b Calculated value. ² Literature value. ¹ Ref. 9. ² Ref. 11. ³ $f/f_o = F(V_E/\bar{v}_o)^{1/3}$. ⁴ Ref. 15. ⁵ Ref. 13. ⁶ Ref. 14.

Complex Formation with some Bidentate Ligands. Part-V. Thermodynamic Aspects of Complexation Reactions of some Bivalent Metal Ions with *vic*-Hydroxyaldehyde Thiosemicarbazones

C. K. BHASKAR*, P. P. HANKARE and R. S. RAMPURE
 Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004
 and
 V. B. MANE

Department of Chemistry, Science College, Satara-416 001

Manuscript received 18 April 1988, accepted 14 December 1988

SALICYLALDEHYDE thiosemicarbazone (SATSC), 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (5-NSATSC) and 4-methylsalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (4-MSATSC) form chelates with many metals. The present paper aims at measuring the thermodynamic formation constants of the chelates of Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Mg^{II} with the above ligands using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF DIVALENT METAL IONS WITH LIGANDS

Ligand	Cation	Stability constant	β at Temp.			$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔS° (J mol ⁻¹)		
			25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	Graphical	Calculated	25°	35°	45°
SATSC	H ⁺	log K ₁ ^H	11.29	10.65	10.33	64.18	62.59	62.63	-85.90	-86.02	-78.27	-75.82	-73.35
	H ⁺	log K ₂ ^H	9.23	8.70	7.73	52.46	50.95	46.89	-189.06	-187.16	-270.48	-265.83	-271.02
	Mg ²⁺	log K ₁	3.00	2.93	2.84	17.09	17.20	17.22	-15.96	-14.80	-8.70	-4.01	-3.95
	Mn ²⁺	log K ₁	4.53	4.20	3.70	25.74	24.69	22.46	-74.52	-75.24	-168.66	-161.45	-168.52
	Zn ²⁺	log K ₁	5.56	5.20	4.38	33.41	30.58	28.57	-151.86	-154.29	-396.30	-393.60	-406.73
	Co ²⁺	log K ₁	7.66	6.30	5.45	43.58	37.05	33.08	-206.96	-198.84	-548.07	-551.07	-546.40
4-MSATSC	H ⁺	log K ₁ ^H	11.70	10.90	10.43	66.57	64.10	63.30	-112.12	-113.76	-156.90	-155.88	-158.66
	H ⁺	log K ₂ ^H	9.75	9.10	8.22	55.47	53.50	49.86	-189.67	-189.63	-292.49	-279.77	-282.41
	Mg ²⁺	log K ₁	4.03	3.76	2.89	22.89	22.17	17.53	-118.46	-108.84	-304.35	-296.90	-302.05
	Cd ²⁺	log K ₁	5.57	5.29	4.38	31.67	31.09	26.56	-109.78	-109.64	-262.06	-255.86	-261.80
	Zn ²⁺	log K ₁	6.59	5.94	4.90	37.48	34.92	29.75	-156.42	-158.87	-399.02	-394.28	-398.43
	Co ²⁺	log K ₁	7.23	6.66	5.66	41.10	39.18	34.38	-140.22	-142.86	-332.57	-327.92	-332.74
5-NSATSC	H ⁺	log K ₁ ^H	11.55	10.95	10.33	63.51	64.43	65.69	-68.87	-64.27	-10.53	-14.41	-10.00
	H ⁺	log K ₂ ^H	10.84	9.20	8.80	58.82	54.09	58.46	-189.67	-187.29	-271.80	-277.50	-271.76
	Mg ²⁺	log K ₁	4.86	4.09	3.70	24.81	23.91	22.46	-57.90	-59.95	-111.08	-110.96	-111.49
	Cd ²⁺	log K ₁	6.98	5.95	5.32	39.39	34.49	32.27	-140.89	-144.74	-338.93	-342.28	-339.94
	Mn ²⁺	log K ₁	8.17	6.34	5.78	46.47	37.28	35.10	-211.08	-212.07	-552.26	-557.28	-552.72
	Zn ²⁺	log K ₁	8.70	6.48	6.18	49.49	40.24	37.51	-280.40	-224.00	-609.50	-617.90	-606.69
Co ²⁺	log K ₁	9.58	8.37	7.89	54.47	49.19	47.94	-150.27	-150.91	-321.80	-327.90	-321.70	

as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The studies were carried out in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium maintaining a constant ionic strength $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) at 25, 35, and 45° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Experimental

Potentiometric titrations were carried out using a Elico LI-120 digital pH meter with a Philips glass-calomel electrode assembly. The readings of pH meter were corrected for solvent effect as previously reported¹.

Salicylaldehyde (AnalaR) was used as such. 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and 4-methylsalicylaldehyde were prepared by standard procedures². Thiosemicarbazones of different aldehydes were prepared³. Carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) solution (0.98 M) was prepared⁴. Solutions of the ligands (0.04 M) were prepared in ethanol. Metal perchlorate solutions were prepared by treating 2 M HClO₄ (20 ml) with excess of the oxide or carbonate of the metal (A.R.) and suitably diluting the resulting solutions to 100 ml of 0.2 M approximately. The metal contents were determined by standard procedures⁵.

Procedure: Following solutions were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution (0.98 M): (i) 4 ml 0.2 M HClO₄+0.78 ml 4 M NaClO₄+20 ml ethanol+15.2 ml distilled water, (ii) 4 ml 0.2 M HClO₄+0.78 ml 4 M NaClO₄+10 ml 0.04 M reagent+10 ml ethanol+15.2 ml distilled water and (iii) 2 ml 0.2 M HClO₄+2 ml 0.02 M metal perchlorate solution containing 0.2 M HClO₄+0.77 ml 4 M NaClO₄+10 ml 0.04 M reagent+10 ml ethanol+15.2 ml distilled water.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by using half-integral, graphical and least-squares methods. The values of average stability constants are given in Table 1.

In case of SATSC and related compounds there is an additional phenolic OH group and *vic*-hydroxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazones undergo first deprotonation in the phenolic OH whereas the second deprotonation in the thiol group. Mono-deprotonated species and di-deprotonated species are formed successively in the first and second processes of ionisations. Ligands are, therefore, likely to be tridentate with oxygen, sulphur and nitrogen as active atoms.

In the present study, 1 : 1 complexes have been identified in the solution form, and 1 : 2 complexes could not be studied as in the high pH range 1 : 2 complexes are precipitated. The log K₁^H and log K₂^H values of the ligands were determined pH metrically at 25, 35 and 45° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) at constant ionic strength $\mu=0.1 M$ (NaClO₄). The values were found to decrease with increase in temperature. The log K₁^H and log K₂^H values for the ligands are in the order, SATSC < 4-MSATSC < 5-NSATSC. In the present study the stability orders are SATSC, Co > Zn > Mn > Mg; 5-NSATSC, Co > Zn > Mn > Cd > Mg; 4-MSATSC, Co > Zn > Cd > Mg, which agree with the earlier reports⁶. The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) accompanying complexation have been calculated by using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation. ΔH° has also been determined with the help of an isobar equation. Thiosemicarbazones form more stable complexes with soft metal ions due to large negative values of ΔH° . We found large negative values of ΔH° for

NOTES

SATSC and substituted-SATSC derivatives with divalent metal ions indicating most stable complexes and formation of stronger metal-ligand bonds. ΔS° values are also large which favour complex formation.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.B.M.) is thankful to Prin. S. D. Patil, Secretary, Rayat Shikshan Sanstha, Satara and Prin. M. A. Shaikh, Science College, Satara for encouragement and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. B. GUTBEZAHLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 565, R. G. BATES and G. SCHWARZENBACH, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1955, **38**, 699; R. G. BATES, "Determination of pH", Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 228.
2. C. C. HACH, L. M. LIGGETT and H. DIEHL, *Iowa State Coll. J. Sci.*, 1947, **27**, 811, J. C. DUFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 547.
3. F. E. ANDERSON, G. J. DUCA and J. V. SCUDT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **73**, 4967.
4. E. P. SERJEANT and A. ALBERT, "Determination of Ionisation Constants", 2nd. ed., Chapman and Hall, London, 1971.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "The Text Book, of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1961.
6. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAM, *Nature (London)*, 1948, **162**, 746, L. E. MALBY and D. P. MELLOR, *Nature (London)*, 1948, **161**, 846, K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. A. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1027.